

Minimization of the Out-of-Plane Thermal Deformation of CFRP Reflectors by Stacking Sequence Optimization

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Background

Space-based, large reflectors (mirrors) are highly demanded to realize high-precision space observatories. Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is regarded as a suitable material for these reflectors. However, it was found that **non-negligible out-of-plane thermal deformation occurs due to fiber orientation error.**

CFRP reflector model used in our previous study.

An example of the out-of-plane thermal deformation of a CFRP reflector model due to fiber orientation error.

In manufacturing process of CFRP laminates, fiber orientation error of 0.4° in standard deviation is unavoidable [1].

In this study, the method to mitigate the effect of the fiber orientation error was investigated.

[1] Y. Arai *et al.*, Effect of ply angle misalignment on out-of-plane deformation of symmetrical cross-ply CFRP laminates: Accuracy of the ply angle misalignment, *Composite Structures*, **93**, 2011, pp. 1225-1230.

Evaluation of the thermal deformation

The curvature of CFRP plates was evaluated.

The standard deviation of the curvature in all directions was evaluated as follows:

The limit value of the standard deviation of the curvature:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^{\pi} \kappa^T(e, \theta)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{\pi} \cdot f(e) d\theta de}$$

Effect of the stacking sequence

Calculated standard deviation of the curvature of quasi-isotropic CFRP plates with some different stacking sequences due to fiber orientation error of 0.4° in standard deviation.

Number of layers	Stacking sequence	Standard deviation of the curvature [$\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}/\text{K}$]
8	[0/-45/90/45] _s	69.93
16	[0 ₂ /-45 ₂ /90 ₂ /45 ₂] _s	49.77
16	[0/-45/90/45] _{2s}	25.73

- Increasing the number of layers (Using thin prepreg)
- Altering the stacking sequence with same number of layers were found to be effective.

Possibility of further suppression by optimizing the stacking sequence.

Stacking sequence optimization

The stacking sequence of the CFRP plates were optimized to minimize the standard deviation of the curvature due to fiber orientation error by means of the genetic algorithm (GA) with following conditions:

- Number of layers: 8 or 16
- Fiber orientation on the uppermost layer: 0°
- Nominal stacking sequence: Symmetric

The history of the highest fitness value for each generation in the optimization by GA.

Calculated standard deviation of the curvature of CFRP plates with optimum stacking sequences due to fiber orientation error of 0.4° in standard deviation.

Number of layers	Stacking sequence	Standard deviation of the curvature [$\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}/\text{K}$]
8	[0/-47.1/71.4/4.2] _s	48.63 (-30%)
16	[0/-56.3/66.8/50.6/-72.1/48.9/-37.3/6.0] _s	21.61 (-16%)

Stacking sequence optimization was demonstrated to be an effective method.